

Condensed 1,8-Naphthyridines. Part-VI. Synthesis of 8-Aryl-8*H*-naphtho[1',2' : 5,6]pyrano[4,3-*b*][1,8]naphthyridines

K. RAJENDAR REDDY, K. MOGILAI AH and B. SREENIVASULU*

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

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The condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1) with substituted-2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl styryl ketones (2) in the presence of glacial acetic acid containing a catalytic amount of concentrated sulphuric acid affords the corresponding 8-aryl-8*H*-naphtho[1',2' : 5,6]pyrano[4,3-*b*][1,8]naphthyridines (3). Structures of the products have been established on the basis of elemental analyses, and ir, pmr and mass spectral data. The compounds were also tested for their antibacterial activity.

In continuation of our earlier reports on the synthesis and biological activity of substituted¹⁻³ and condensed⁴⁻⁸ [1,8]naphthyridines, we describe in this paper the synthesis of hitherto unreported 8-aryl-8*H*-naphtho[1',2' : 5,6]pyrano[4,3-*b*][1,8]naphthyridines. The study was undertaken in view of the fact that 2,3-fused 1,8-naphthyridines⁹⁻¹¹ have a wide spectrum of biological activity. The synthetic approach to the title compounds is outlined in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The present paper deals with a facile synthesis of 8-aryl-8*H*-naphtho[1',2' : 5,6]pyrano[4,3-*b*][1,8]naphthyridines (3) in good yield, involving the condensation of substituted-2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl styryl ketones (2) with 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1) in the presence of glacial acetic acid containing a catalytic amount of concentrated sulphuric acid.

A plausible mechanism for the formation of 3 is shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

Experimental

All the m.ps. reported are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded in nujol on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian 60 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a Varian MAT CH-7 instrument. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through tlc.

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl styryl ketones: Various 2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl styryl ketones derived from 1-acetyl-2-naphthol and benzaldehydes were prepared by the literature method¹².

8-Aryl-8*H*-naphtho[1',2' : 5,6]pyrano[4,3-*b*][1,8]naphthyridine: An equimolar mixture of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1; 0.1 mol) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl styryl ketone (2; 0.1 mol) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid for 5 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and poured on to crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

By adopting similar procedure, a few substituted-naphthopyrano[1,8]naphthyridines were synthesised. The characteristics of the compounds are recorded in Table 1.

The structures of these compounds have been confirmed on the basis of chemical, elemental

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF 8-ARYL-8H-NAPHTHO[1',2':5,6]PYRANO[4,3-b][1,8]NAPHTHYRIDINES (3)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)		
					C	H	N
1.	C ₆ H ₅	>300	66	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	83.40 (83.33)	4.52 (4.44)	7.85 (7.78)
2.	4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	>300	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	80.05 (80.00)	4.69 (4.61)	7.13 (7.17)
3.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	>300	72	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	83.48 (83.42)	4.87 (4.81)	7.53 (7.49)
4.	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	>300	76	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ ClO	76.09 (76.14)	3.73 (3.81)	7.15 (7.11)
5.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	>300	82	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ ClO	76.08 (76.14)	3.74 (3.81)	7.14 (7.11)
6.	2-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	>300	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	74.10 (74.07)	3.75 (3.70)	10.31 (10.37)
7.	3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	>300	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	74.13 (74.07)	3.73 (3.70)	10.35 (10.37)
8.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	>300	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	79.68 (79.78)	4.19 (4.25)	7.40 (7.44)
9.	4-N,N-(OH) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	>300	76	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ O	80.45 (80.39)	5.26 (5.21)	10.40 (10.42)
10.	1-Naphthyl	>300	65	C ₂₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	84.82 (84.88)	4.45 (4.39)	6.88 (6.88)
11.	2-Furyl	>300	68	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	78.75 (78.86)	4.02 (4.00)	8.06 (8.00)
12.	2-Thienyl	>300	70	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO	75.47 (75.41)	3.88 (3.83)	7.69 (7.65)

analyses, ir, pmr and mass spectral studies. Negative tests with neutral ferric chloride and 2,4-DNP indicate the absence of phenolic hydroxyl and carboxyl groups in the products.

The ir spectra show the absence of bands due to OH and COOH groups, and the presence of a strong band at 1600 cm⁻¹ attributable to C=N. The mass spectrum of 3 showed a strong molecular ion peak at *m/z* 394. The structures of naphthopyrano[1,8]naphthyridines were also confirmed by pmr spectral studies. The pmr spectrum of 3 (R=4-CH₃O.C₆H₄) in DMSO-d₆ exhibited a three-proton singlet at δ 3.7 assignable to methoxyl group, a singlet at 6.0 due to benzylic proton, and a complex multiplet at 6.4–8.5 for fourteen aromatic protons.

Antibacterial activity: All the compounds were tested for antibacterial activity by filter paper disc technique¹⁸ using a species of gram-negative bacteria, *i.e.* *E. coli* and *P. vulgaris*, and a species of gram-positive bacteria, *i.e.* *B. Substillus* and *S. albus*. None of the compounds showed any promising activity.

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